

ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS OF MOISTURE ON GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Glass fiber polymer composites are used for constructing wind turbine blades as these materials have high specific strength and stiffness, good fatigue properties and low cost. Increasing the turbine size to create an economy of scale has pushed the wind industry offshore. Throughout the lifetime of offshore wind turbine blades the mechanical properties degrade, with the high humidity conditions being a predominant cause. In order to understand and quantify the mechanism(s) of degradation, a simulation of the environmental moisture conditions was performed by immersing glass fiber reinforced polymer specimens in salt water for a period of up to seven years. The mechanical properties of the specimens tested before and after humidity conditioning were compared and analysed to evaluate the damage effects and degradation mechanisms. In addition, single fiber tensile testing was performed under different moisture conditions. The diffusion mechanism of water in the polymer was studied to quantify the diffusion coefficients and define which parameters increase the rate of water absorption (e.g. salt concentration, sample geometry and fiber direction). Three different degradation processes of the composite were observed: polymer plasticization, fiber stress corrosion and interface degradation, where the latter was found to be the most detrimental for the application of such materials for wind turbines.

1. Introduction

Lightweight structural applications often require the use of composite materials, which have superior properties and are tailorable to a particular application. Composites have high specific strength and stiffness values, good fatigue properties, interesting chemical resistance, and in the case of glass fiber composites, an acceptable cost.

One major application for glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRP) is the wind industry, where the size of the windmill rotor blades is increasingly large. The installation of new wind farms is often offshore (due to higher available wind speeds and in order to avoid competition with agriculture and other land use). The high relative humidity offshore can degrade the rotor blades during their lifetime. In order to predict and design structures capable of withstanding these conditions, it is necessary to quantify and understand the effects of moisture on the mechanical properties of the composite materials. It is important to determine the

mechanisms that initiate and progress degradation in order to understand the overall process.

The degradation of the mechanical properties of GFRP as a result of the environmental conditions of moisture has previously been studied [1,2]. The immersion of glass fiber composite specimens in water has been a common method for simulating the environmental effects of moisture on these materials. The layup configuration for most of these specimens was multidirectional.

The effects of degradation are only noticeable at long periods of immersion, as generally the rates of water absorption are small. Understanding the water diffusion process is important as reducing the diffusion coefficient slows the process of degradation.

As offshore wind installations are very expensive, maximizing the energy captured of the wind turbines it is essential. This translates to increasing the size of the turbines (for example studies performed within the Upwind project funded under the EU's Sixth framework programme) specifically designed for the challenging offshore conditions. Elastic properties of wind turbine blades are a

constraining design parameter, because the operational strain in the blades needs to be minimized in order to withstand degradation effects of fatigue over the lifetime. When environmental effects of moisture reduce the elastic properties of a composite wind turbine blade, the working strain increases (because working loads are, on average, constant) and hence the lifetime is reduced. To identify where and how degradation occurs in the composite, the mechanical performance of a specific parameter is correlated to a physical effect. For example, the longitudinal Young's modulus of a laminate can be correlated to the fibers, the transverse and the shear elastic modulus are correlated to the fiber, matrix and bond between the fiber and the matrix.

2. Background

Interface degradation

The glass fibers in the composite are coated with "sizing", generally an organo-silane that forms an interface with the matrix. The sizing has several functions [3,4]: it protects the fiber during handling; covers singularities at the surface of the glass fiber and therefore increases the strength of the fibers; protects the fibers against humidity and other environmental conditions; and improves adhesion between the matrix and the fiber.

In the early generations of glass fiber composites there was no sizing on the fibers. Problems with strength reductions as result of moisture uptake were observed and it was concluded that a protective coating for the fiber was necessary [4]. Despite ongoing research in the glass fiber industry for several years, degradation of GFRP composites due to environmental moisture continues. The damage is mostly observed in the sizing and leads to unprotected areas on the glass fiber surface.

Significant interfacial degradation has been observed in GFRP composites exposed to water [5], where water absorbed into the polymer concentrates at the hydrophilic interface between the fiber and polymer and initiates degradation. This effect is more pronounced in the case of silane coupling agents [4].

In some GFRP based on epoxy and unsaturated polyester matrices, the reduction in the interface adhesion due to moisture is reversible; i.e. the properties of the material recover when it dries [4]. Also, the oxane molecules in the sizing hydrolyze in the presence of water, reducing the adhesion to the polymer and leading to a poorer quality interface [4]. This damage to the interface increases the number of singularities in the fiber and reduces the adherence between the fibers and the matrix [6].

Matrix plasticization

Matrix plasticization describes a process in which water affects the mechanical properties of the polymer matrix. The elastic modulus and the strength of the polymer depend on its glass transition temperature [7]. When exposed to moisture, water fills the free volume of the polymer and reduces the glass transition temperature. Accompanying this is a shift in the temperature curve of the modulus and an overall reduction in the modulus of the polymer [8]. The reduction of the glass transition temperature leads to different mechanical properties; while the strength reduces, the ultimate strain increases. Thus, the plasticization effect softens a polymer when it is exposed to water for extended periods [9].

Diffusion process

A method for simulating environmental effects of moisture in polymer composites is to use accelerated ageing i.e. immersing polymer laminates in water. High rates of water absorption are achieved which highlight the most critical degradation mechanisms in the composites in humid environments. The water diffusion process is controlled by a concentration gradient of water molecules between the surface and the bulk of the polymer. Water diffusion in the polymer has previously been described as both Fickian [5,10–12] and non-Fickian [11,13] behavior. Here, diffusion coefficients for the laminate are calculated from the weight fraction of the resin (polymer) in the composite and the water diffusion coefficient in the resin (obtained from literature [13]). The

water content at saturation is the point in the degradation process where it is assumed that the water molecules begin interacting with the fiber/polymer interface throughout the sample. The time from when the water reaches the interface to when damage in the fiber is first observed, depends on the resistance of the sizing to water. Water diffusion coefficients can only provide information about the water content in the composite for a limited amount of time. The probability for water to interact with the interface increases with the water content in the sample, which is obviously maximal when saturated.

Hygro-strains

The polymer expands when water is absorbed into the matrix, and the coefficient of moisture expansion (CME) is defined as the fractional strain increase per unit mass as a result of the water uptake. The CME value of epoxies is typically $3.24 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (1/%) [12] and it is usually assumed that the fiber does not absorb water (negligible CME). As the fiber and matrix are strongly bonded in the composite material, an expansion mismatch due to the moisture absorption creates “hygro-strains”.

The behavior of these hygro-strains during mechanical testing depends on the loading direction with respect to the fiber direction, as the expansion mismatch puts the fiber in tension and the matrix in compression. Along the fiber direction the hygro-strains contribute with a tensile pre-straining, and in the transverse direction with a compressive pre-straining. The effects of the hygro-strains disappear when the water is removed from the polymer (if permanent damage to the laminate has not occurred). Hygro-strains are typically in the order of 0.005 % to 0.05 % of strain depending on the water content of the sample.

Stress corrosion

Static fatigue can cause premature failure of a single fiber over time when water interacts with the glass surface. Chemical processes occur at sites of structural flaws, where the concentration of cations at the surface of the fiber interrupts the silica network [14]. Hydrolysis reactions

between the water molecules and cations lead to an increase in the concentration of hydroxyl ions. The resulting increase in pH can reach a critical level for corrosion to occur. Water combined with stresses at the surface of the fiber activates static fatigue (stress corrosion) which in two ways can initiate fractures over time (1) the continuous reduction in surface energy as a function of the environment that corrodes the fiber and (2) continuous growth of the crack which increases the stress intensity at the crack tip [15]. This coupling effect arises because when a crack in the fiber surface grows, the amount of material exposed to the environment increased, accelerating the ageing, and vice versa the corrosive environment reduces the surface energy density and cracks develop faster. This process has been described in two stages that precede fracture; (1) an incubation period where the water reacts with cations in the glass leading to hydrolysis and an increase in the concentration of hydroxyl ions [4,14], (2) corrosion occurs when a critical concentration of the hydroxyl ions is reached. The corrosion stage is short compared to the fiber lifetime and occurs only under stresses high enough to allow total failure in the time available for fracture [14].

Singularities and strength

The strength of a brittle material like glass depends on the intrinsic fracture toughness and the distribution of flaws (size, orientation and position) in the material, where the latter act as initiation sites for cracks [16]. E-glass fibers have irregular surfaces containing flaws [17], however, the sizing coating covers many irregularities/flaws, helping to reduce the crack density at the surface.

A previous study within the OPTIMAT project at DTU (formerly Risø) [18] showed that longitudinal specimens made from unidirectional laminates reduced in strength when immersed in water. However, for the same type of specimens, the Young’s modulus did not show degradation after long periods of immersion.

Motivation of this study

In this study the degradation of the mechanical properties of glass fiber composites exposed to

long periods of immersion is investigated and the related mechanisms of diffusion and causes of degradations are analyzed. The present work continues some studies initiated in the OPTIMAT project [18], and some specimens used here came from a plan of long-term conditioning established there.

3. Method and materials

In order to investigate the effect of long-term moisture exposure on the composites, long-term specimens were immersed in salt water for a period up to eight years [18]. Short-term conditioning was also performed in order to obtain the diffusion coefficients of water in the laminates.

For both long- and short-term conditioning samples, E-glass fibers with an average diameter of 17 μm (embedded in epoxy resin) were used. The sizing material was an organo-silane compatible with epoxy, unsaturated polyester, and vinyl-ester.

Two types of laminates were prepared; (1) unidirectional (UD) – a laminate with the same fiber orientation for all layers and (2) multidirectional (MD) which had as a layup configuration $[[\pm 45, 0^\circ]_4; \pm 45]$. The specimens were labeled “longitudinal” or “transversal” referring to the fiber orientation in the UD laminates or the fiber orientation of the main layer of the MD laminates.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of UD, MD and pure resin specimens at the reference state from OPTIMAT project

Sample Type	Batch's name	Test Type	Fiber direction [Degrees]	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]
UD	Ref-UD-T-90	Tension	90	13.57 0.71	55 2.57
	Ref-UD-S-0	Shear	0	5.50 0.49	74 4.17
	Ref-UD-S-90	Shear	90	4.80 0.20	71 4.27
MD	Ref-MD-T-0	Tension	0	28.43 0.91	555 18.43
	Ref-MD-T-90	Tension	90	14.84 0.81	144 3.2
Pure resin	Ref-M-T	Tension	-	3.07 0.19	68 0.32
	Ref-M-S	Shear	-	1.16 0.04	40 0.90

The initial mechanical properties of UD, MD and pure epoxy resin (reference state) specimens are shown in Table 1. The averages values of the mechanical properties are shown in bold while the standard deviation are below them. These values are used for comparison with the conditioned samples to quantify the degradation after long periods of immersion.

Specimens immersed for short periods of time (used to characterize the diffusion coefficients of salt water in the composite materials) were also longitudinal and transverse samples obtained from UD and MD laminates.

Table 2 shows the sample type and test details for each specimen. The effect of salt concentration in the water was analyzed by immersing the specimens in either; (1) distilled water, (2) water with 24.53 g/L of NaCl (standard for sea water substitute ASTM D1141) and (3) water with 49.06 g/L of NaCl (double the salt concentration of sea water). The pH values of all solutions were adjusted (using 0.1 N NaOH solution as per instructions in the standard) to 8.5, the same pH as the water used for long periods of immersion. It was assumed that a short period of immersion could not

initiate stress corrosion in the fiber as there was insufficient time for the water to reach the fiber surface. Hence, the Na^+ cations used to adjust the pH of the water are assumed to have no effect.

Table 2 Conditioning, test type and layups for short-term immersion specimens

Batch's name	Layup	Test type	Salt concentration referred to ASTM	Immersion time [h]
Short-UD-S-90-out of plane	UD	Shear	Standard	2500
Short-UD-T-90	UD	Tension	Standard	1800
Short-MD-T-00	MD	Tension	Distilled Standard Double Stand.	1800

The samples were weighed every week (for a period of 15 weeks) using a Mettler Toledo AB304-S/FACT balance. The samples were measured two hours after removal from the water tanks. Specimens conditioned for short periods did not include the tabs (usually placed in the grip zone for mechanical measurements) to allow better diffusion of the water over the entire specimen.

The elastic properties were measured according to the standard ISO 527/4 (5) in the case of tension, and ASTM D5379 for performing isopescu tests. The standard strain range used to measure the elastic properties was 0.05 % to 0.25 %, except for transverse UD specimens with fibers oriented perpendicularly to the loading force where 0.05 % to 0.15 % was used. The latter have a lower measurable range of elastic properties due to the very low ultimate strains.

In order to understand the effects of moisture on a glass fiber under an applied strain (stress corrosion), single fiber tensile testing was performed at 50 % relative humidity (RH) or room conditions, and inside of a dry glove box considered to be at 0 % RH. OCV fibers from Owens Corning with an average diameter of 15.5 μm were used. The tensile apparatus used

in both cases was the same; consisting of a balance to measure the load and a micrometer to measure the displacement. The modulus was measured from the last point of fracture assuming that the fibers were linearly elastic up to the failure point.

4. Results

Yi and Hilton [19] presented a formula to calculate the diffusion parameters of composite laminates from the volume fractions and diffusion coefficients of the bulk materials. Within the assumptions, the fibers do not absorb water and there is no moisture propagation through cracks. The diffusion coefficients and retardation times shown in Table 3 are prony values obtained through iteration for the epoxy resin used. These values were used in the model presented in [13] to calculate the diffusion curves of water uptake in the laminate as a function of time (as shown in Fig.1 along with models of both non-Fickian and Fickian diffusion). It can be clearly seen that the experimental results fit well to a non-Fickian behavior, which indicates that there are mechanisms in the process of water uptake that change the diffusion coefficient with time [13].

Table 3 Diffusion coefficient (D) and retardation time (τ_r) of epoxy immersed in salt water at 23 °C degrees.

	D (mm^2/s) $\times 10^{-7}$	τ_r (s)
Non-Fickian	D0	2.690
	D1	-1.838
	D2	0.388
	D3	0.542
	D4	2.997
	D5	-2.852
Fickian	D6	-1.084
	D	1.460

The rate of water absorption in transverse specimens is more susceptible to the fiber volume content than longitudinal specimens (as a larger area of the sample is a cross section of the fibers).

All short-term conditioning samples showed non-Fickian diffusion behavior. The non-Fickian curve for specimens immersed in water with the standard salt concentration uses the diffusion

coefficients shown in Table 3 as reference values. The diffusion coefficients in distilled water and water with the double salt concentration of the standard are half and four times, respectively, the value of the reference diffusion coefficients. The results shown in Fig. 2 indicate that the rate of water absorption increases with the salt concentration of the water. The possibility of salt molecules crystallizing on the surface of the samples and adding to the measured weight has not been ruled out and hence these data should be viewed with caution. The water uptake for a fixed time for the specimens shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 (exposed to the same salt concentration) was different, because the shape, fiber direction and geometry of the samples were different. However, the same diffusion coefficients for the bulk materials were observed. For iosipescu samples the water uptake was faster than in the longitudinal MD specimens from Fig. 2 because the iosipescu samples were out of plane (fiber direction perpendicular to the largest area of the sample). This indicates that the diffusion of water is faster along the fiber direction than perpendicular to it.

Fig. 1. Water content as a function of the squared root of time for Iosipescu specimens.

The worst scenario for the composites is that the water reaches the fiber during the service lifetime and stress corrosion in the fiber occurs. Tensile testing of single fibers without a matrix at different moisture conditions shows how

important the effects of moisture are on the mechanical properties of glass fibers. Table 4 shows a 28.6 % strength reduction in specimens that were tested at room conditions (50 % RH) compared to specimens tested inside the glove box (0 % RH). However, the elastic modulus is not affected by stress corrosion; Table 4 shows that the calculated modulus for both batches of samples overlap (as expected) and also indicates reproducibility of the technique.

Fig. 2. Water content as a function of the squared root of time for longitudinal MD specimens immersed in different salt concentration waters at short-term of conditioning.

Table 4 Single fiber tensile test on OCV fibers tested at 50% RH and 0% RH

	RH [%]	Diameter [μm]	Modulus [MPa]	Strength [MPa]
Mean	0	16.06	84380	2147
95% conf.		0.28	3762	100
Mean	50	15.38	82168	1533
95% Conf.		0.42	2102	153

For short immersion times it is assumed that the water does not reach the fiber and the absorbed water does not degrade the elastic properties of the laminates. However, the final properties (strength and ultimate strain) of the sample might change because of an elastic effect of residual strains inside the polymer, due to hygro-strains from expansion mismatch. The large standard deviation in the strength of glass fibers (due to surface flaws) complicates the

picture when looking for a clear effect of hygro strains on the strength or ultimate strain of the samples. The hygro-strains are smaller than the standard deviation of the ultimate strain. In fact the largest hygro-strain calculated using the

CME of epoxy and the maximum water uptake is 0.010 %, which is less than the smallest standard deviation for the ultimate strain of the samples tested.

Table 5 Mechanical properties of specimens after long-term conditioning

Sample Type	Batch's name	Test Type	Fiber direction [Degrees]	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]
UD	Long-UD-T-90	Tension	90	11.93 0.13	46.78 2.57
	Long-UD-S-0	Shear	0	4.69 0.24	65.07 2.58
	Long -UD-S-90	Shear	90	4.26 0.19	47.12 1.93
MD	Long -MD-T-0	Tension	0	26.37 0.4	423.76 10.08
	Long -MD-T-90	Tension	90	12.89 0.06	124.32 0.08
Pure resin	Long -M-T	Tension	-	2.82 0.01	50.94 7.83
	Long -M-S	Shear	-	1.08 0.02	39.05 0.25

The elastic properties of a laminate depend on the direction of analysis. Along the fiber the elasticity of the laminate depends highly on the elastic properties of the fiber. In the direction perpendicular to the fiber, and similarly in shear, the elasticity of the laminate shows a mechanical response dependent on many factors including the polymer matrix, the fiber, and the interface between the two. Table 5 shows the elastic Young's modulus and strengths of specimens immersed for long periods. Both tension and shear properties were characterized for MD and UD laminates having longitudinal and transverse fiber directions.

Pure epoxy resin specimens (prepared and tested under the same conditions as the composites) showed ~ 25 % degradation in strength and an 8 % reduction in the modulus of elasticity, as shown in Fig. 3.

Degradation in the interface quality is likely the reason for the reduction in the unidirectional transverse modulus, unidirectional shear modulus, multidirectional elastic modulus and strength in all composite specimens.

Fig. 3. Normalized tensile properties of epoxy resin specimens both dry (reference), and immersed in sea water substitute for over 63400 h.

The results obtained for tensile tests of transverse UD specimens after long-term conditioning showed a 12 % degradation in the elastic modulus and a 15 % reduction in the strength compared to the reference state (see Fig. 4). Also shown are results obtained in the OPTIMAT project for specimens conditioned at

6 and 12 months of immersion. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show mechanical properties of samples conditioned for 6 months (also from the OPTIMAT project).

Fig. 4. Normalized tensile properties of transverse unidirectional specimens immersed for different periods in sea water substitute.

Fig. 5. Normalized shear properties of transverse unidirectional specimens immersed for different periods in sea water substitute.

Degradation of the shear properties of unidirectional laminates was also observed. For iosipescu specimens with a fiber direction perpendicular to the loading force, the elastic shear modulus and the shear strength reduced by 16 % and 12 %, respectively, as shown in Fig. 6. For specimens with the fiber direction parallel to the loading force the reduction in the elastic shear modulus and strength were 12 % and 34 %, respectively.

Fig. 6. Normalized tensile properties of longitudinal multi-directional specimens immersed for different periods in sea water substitute

Longitudinal multidirectional specimens showed a 7 % reduction in the elastic modulus and a 24 % reduction in the longitudinal strength after long periods of immersion. The former is assumed to be degradation resulting from a reduction in the elastic modulus of the biaxial layers. After long-term immersion, transverse multidirectional specimens showed a reduction of 13 % in the elastic modulus and of 14 % in the strength. These values are very similar to those obtained for the transverse unidirectional samples, indicating that degradation in the modulus of elasticity in biaxial layers is proportional to those in the transverse unidirectional layers. The reduction in transversal strength of the multidirectional laminates is less than that of the longitudinal strength of the multidirectional laminate because in the transverse direction the stress corrosion of the fiber is not the dominant degradation mechanism.

The elastic degradation of the polymeric material alone cannot explain the overall reduction in the transverse and shear elastic modulus of the unidirectional laminate. Also, it was shown that degradation in the elastic properties of the fiber does not occur when in the laminated form, neither when exposed completely to a humid environment. Therefore, it is assumed that the bond between the matrix and the fibers is the predominant mechanism of degradation of the elastic properties of glass fiber composite specimens immersed for long

periods in sea water. This effect is proposed to occur as water hydrolyzes the oxane molecules in the sizing, reducing adhesion with the polymer and leading to degradation [6].

5. Conclusions

A non-Fickian diffusion behavior was observed in GFRP composites immersed in salt water solutions. The rate of water absorption may increase with salt concentration and in the direction along the fibers. The diffusion coefficients and retardation times for non-Fickian diffusion were used to calculate the water content of a laminate after a certain immersion time.

Degradation in the elastic properties of UD samples of 12 % and 16 % in the transverse and shear modulus, respectively, was observed, for a period of up to eight years of immersion. This result is consistent with the reduction in the elastic modulus of MD specimens of 7 % and 13 % in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. This reduction in the elastic properties of GFRP composites is explained by a degradation of the bonding between the fiber and the matrix.

A reduction in the fiber tensile strength was seen, resulting from stress corrosion and the opening of singularities in the glass fiber. Tensile testing of single glass fibers showed a drop of 28 % in the strength in an environment with 50 % RH, close to the reduction of 24 % in the strength of longitudinal MD GFRP specimens immersed in salt water for long periods.

These degradation effects on both the strength and elastic properties of GFRP materials might impose constraints on the design of structures like wind turbine blades that are placed offshore. Although the effects of the moisture environment might not directly affect the elastic modulus of the fiber, degradation of the interface between the fiber and the matrix indirectly (in the case of biaxial laminates or in the transversal direction) affect the elasticity and therefore the lifetime of the structure.

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7. References

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